

A Mathematical Frame Work for Peristaltic Mechanism of a Bingham Fluid in an Elastic Permeable Tube

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Abstract - Peristaltic transport of a Bingham fluid flow in an elastic tube with permeable wall is investigated. The problem is formulated by considering the radial motion of the tube wall. The flow is axisymmetric. The governing equations of motion are solved in a wave frame of reference under low Reynolds number and long wavelength approximation. The effects of various pertinent parameters on variation of flux are calculated and discussed through graphs. It is noticed that the flux enhances with increasing values of amplitude ratio due to increase in maximum displacement of the fluid particles. The flux increases with increasing the values of outlet pressure but opposite behaviour is observed in the case of inlet pressure.

Keywords: Bingham fluid, axisymmetric flow, elastic parameters, permeable wall, peristaltic transport

I Introduction

Most of the earlier research works were made on peristaltic pumping of non-Newtonian fluids through channels/tubes to analyze the flow behavior of physiological fluids. The present study is modeled by considering the flow through a flexible tube to describe the rheological characteristics of blood flow in a small blood vessel due to their elastic nature which has many practical biomedical applications. Peristalsis is an important mechanism which can be observed in physiological systems. This mechanism is mainly used in the roller pumps in the industries and for transporting blood in heart lung machine. The fluids of practical interest are Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids, depending on the various conditions. The analysis of peristaltic pumping of non-Newtonian fluids in different type of geometries has drawn more attention among researchers due to a various applications in biomedical and industrial fields. Also, Permeability is an important property which used to understand the influence of tissue region in the blood flow. In view of such significant physiological and engineering applications, a numerous theoretical and experimental investigations were attempted to understand peristalsis mechanism by researchers for various fluids subject to different conditions.

After the first experimental investigation of Latham [1] on peristaltic pumping, Shapiro et al. [2] presented a detailed analysis of peristaltic flow of Newtonian fluid along with experimental results. The perturbation solution in powers of amplitude ratio was applied by Burns and Parkes [3] in two different cases, one is the peristaltic motion without pressure gradient and another one is flow under prescribed pressure with sinusoidal varying cross section in a fixed channel walls. The periodical change in the diameter of vasomotion of blood vessels involving peristalsis was considered by Fung and Yih [4]. Thereafter a number of analytical and numerical studies pertaining to the flow on

Newtonian fluids with peristalsis were considered by many researchers in different physical constraints. Mishra et al., [5], , Vajravelu et al., [6], AR Rao et al., [7], Hayat et al., [8], Nadeem and Akbar [9]

Roach and Burton [10] presented experimental results on non – Newtonian flow through collapsible elastic tubes. Mishra and Ghosh [11] considered a mathematical model for Hemodynamic flows which is studied by considering pulsatile flow of a viscous fluid in a porous elastic vessel with variable cross-section. Vajravelu et al. [12] studied the case of inserting a catheter in to an elastic tube to analyze the variations in blood flow pattern by considering Herschel –Bulkley fluid. Takaghi and Balmforth [13] applied lubrication analysis study the pumping efficiency. The influence of peristalsis on Herschel –Bulkley fluid flow through elastic tube was examined by Vajravelu et al. [15]. Sochi [14] used lubrication approximation to understand the flow behavior of Newtonian fluid and power-law fluid in elastic tubes by considering the pressure-area constitutive relation. Vajravelu et al. [16] discussed the Casson fluid flow through an elastic tube with peristalsis and analyzed that Rubinow and Keller model is better than the Mazumdar model. Badari Narayana et al. [17] analyzed the effects of elasticity on Herschel-Bulkley fluid flow in a tube. Srinivas et al., [18] investigated the peristaltic transport of a Generalized Newtonian fluid flow in an elastic tube. Lakshminarayana et al. [19] investigated the effects of Joule heating and slip on peristaltic flow of a Bingham fluid in an inclined tapered porous channel with elastic walls.

Motivated by above studies it is essential to study the effect of elasticity on Bingham fluid flow in a tube. The variation of flux is calculated by Rubinow and Keller [20]. The influence of various pertinent parameters on variation of flux along the tube radius for a Bingham fluid through elastic tube with permeable walls are calculated and interpreted through graphs.

II Mathematical Formulation

Consider the steady incompressible laminar peristaltic flow of a Bingham fluid in elastic tube with porous walls.

$a'(z)$ and L are radius and length of the tube respectively. The flow is axisymmetric and cylindrical coordinate system is chosen to study the problem. The wall is subjected to periodic peristaltic movement with wave speed C , wavelength λ , and amplitude b and its instantaneous radius at any axial station z is given by

$$R = a'(z, t) = a_0 + b \sin \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (Z - ct), \quad (1)$$

Figure 1.1 Physical Model

We assume that the tube length is an integral multiple of the wavelength λ and the flow rate is of inertia-free. Under these assumptions, the momentum equation governing the non-Newtonian Bingham fluid flow is given by

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r \tau_{rz}) = - \frac{\partial p}{\partial z}, \tag{2}$$

where τ_{rz} is the shear stress of the Bingham fluid and is given by

$$\tau_{rz} = \mu \left(- \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right) + \tau_0, \quad \tau_{rz} > \tau_0 \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \tag{3a}$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} = 0, \quad \tau_{rz} < \tau_0 \tag{3b}$$

Here u is the axial velocity, p is the pressure, and τ_0 is the yield stress of the tube. If $\tau_{rz} < \tau_0$ there is a core region which flows as a plug and equation (3b) corresponds to vanishing velocity gradient in that region. However, the fluid model we use here is as indicated above for $\tau_{rz} > \tau_0$. The boundary conditions are

$$\tau_{rz} \text{ is finite at } r = 0 \tag{4a}$$

$$u = -c - \beta \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \text{ at } r = a'(z, t) \tag{4b}$$

To solve the equation (2) and (3a) subject to the boundary conditions (4a) and (4b), we introduce the following non-dimensional quantities

$$\bar{r} = \frac{r}{a_0}, \bar{r}_0 = \frac{r_0}{a_0}, \bar{a}' = \frac{a'}{a_0}, \bar{a}'' = \frac{a''}{a_0}, \bar{z} = \frac{z}{\lambda}, \bar{u} = \frac{u}{c}, \bar{t} = \frac{ct}{\lambda}, \bar{\phi} = \frac{b}{a_0},$$

$$\bar{Q} = \frac{Q}{\pi a_0^2 c}, \bar{T} = \frac{T}{\lambda \mu \left(\frac{c}{a_0}\right)}, \bar{p} = \frac{a_0^2}{L \mu c} p, \bar{\tau}_{rz} = \frac{\tau_{rz}}{\mu \left(\frac{c}{a_0}\right)}, \bar{\tau}_0 = \frac{\tau_0}{\mu \left(\frac{c}{a_0}\right)}$$
(5)

Here, $P = -\partial p / \partial z$, a_0 is the radius of the tube in the absence of elasticity, L is the length of the tube, c is the wave speed, and r_0 is the radius of the plug flow region. The governing equations (after dropping the bars) become

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r \tau_{rz}) = P$$
(6)

where τ_{rz} is the shear stress of the Bingham fluid and is given by

$$\tau_{rz} = \left(-\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right) + \tau_0, \quad \tau_{rz} > \tau_0$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} = 0, \quad \tau_{rz} < \tau_0$$

The non-dimensional boundary conditions are

$$\tau_{rz} \text{ is finite at } r = 0$$
(7a)

$$\tau_{rz} = \left(-\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right) + \tau_0, \quad \tau_{rz} > \tau_0$$
(7b)

Solving equation (6) subjected to the conditions (7a) and (7b) we get the velocity field as

$$u = \frac{1}{P} \left[\left(\frac{P}{2} a' - \tau_0 \right)^2 - \left(\frac{P}{2} r - \tau_0 \right)^2 \right] + \beta \left[\frac{P a'}{2} - \tau_0 \right] - 1$$
(8)

Using the boundary condition $\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} = 0$ at $r = r_0$, the upper limit of the plug flow region is given as

$$r_0 = \frac{2\tau_0}{P}$$
(9)

Using the condition $\tau_{rz} = \tau_{a'}$ at $r = a'$ (Bird et al. 1967) we obtain

$$P = \frac{2\tau_{a'}}{a'}$$
(10)

$$\text{Hence } \frac{r_0}{a'} = \frac{\tau_0}{\tau_{a'}} = \tau, \quad 0 < \tau < 1. \tag{11}$$

Using relation (11) and taking $r = r_0$ in equation (8), we obtain the plug flow velocity as

$$u_p = \frac{Pa'^2}{4}(1-\tau)^2 + \frac{\beta Pa'}{2}(1-\tau) - 1 \quad \text{for } 0 \leq r \leq r_0 \tag{12}$$

The volume flux Q through any cross-section is given by

$$Q = 2 \int_0^{r_0} u_p r dr + 2 \int_{r_0}^{a'} u r dr = P [F_1 a'^4 + F_2 a'^3] - \frac{a'^2}{2} \tag{13}$$

$$\text{where } F_1 = \frac{1}{4}(1-\tau)^2 \left[1 - \frac{(1-\tau)(\tau+3)}{6} \right]; F_2 = \frac{\beta}{2}(1-\tau)$$

The above equation (13) gives the volume flux for a tube due to peristalsis with varying radius $a'(z, t)$ in the absence of elasticity. Also the variation arises due to elasticity of the tube wall which is discussed in the next section.

III Theoretical determination of flux

We now find the steady flux Q of an incompressible Bingham fluid of viscosity μ in an elastic tube (see figure 1) of radius $a(z, t) = a'(z, t) + a''(z)$ where $a'(z, t)$ is due to the peristalsis and $a''(z)$ is due to the elastic nature of the tube and length L . We assume that the fluid enters the tube with the pressure p_1 and leaves it with pressure p_2 , while pressure outside the tube is p_0 . If z denotes the distance along the tube from the inlet end, then the pressure $p(z)$ in the fluid at z decreases from $p(0) = p_1$ to $p(1) = p_2$. As a consequence of the pressure difference $p(z) - p_0$, between the inside and outside of the tube, the tube may expand or contract, and tube may deform due to the elastic property of the wall. Therefore the conductivity σ_1 of the tube at z is dependent on the pressure difference. We consider $\sigma_1 = \sigma_1 [p(z) - p_0]$ as a known function of $(p(z) - p_0)$. Let Q is related to the pressure gradient by the relation

$$Q = \sigma(p - p_0)P \tag{14}$$

Where

$$\sigma(p - p_0) = F_1 a'^4 + F_2 a'^3 \tag{15}$$

Considering elastic property in addition to peristaltic movement of the tube wall into consideration, Eq. (15) becomes

$$\sigma(p - p_0) = F_1(a' + a'')^4 + F_2(a' + a'')^3 \tag{16}$$

As the flow is of Poiseuille type, at each cross section, the radius a'' is a function of pressure $p - p_0$, $a''(p - p_0)$ and the wall deformation due to peristalsis is represented by $a'(z) = 1 + \phi \sin 2\pi(z - t)$ which is a function of z . Integrating equation (14) with respect to z from $z = 0$ and using the inlet condition $p(0) = p_1$, we obtain

$$Qz + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^z a'^2 dz = \int_{p(z)-p_0}^{p_1-p_0} (\sigma(p')) dp' \tag{17}$$

where $p' = p(z) - p_0$. This equation determines $p(z)$ implicitly in terms of Q and z . To find Q , we set $z = 1$ and $p(1) = p_2$ in equation (17) to obtain

$$q^n = \int_{p(1)-p_0}^{p_1-p_0} (\sigma(p'))^n dp', \tag{18}$$

Now, using (16) in (18), we have

$$Q + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\phi^2}{4} = \int_{p(1)-p_0}^{p_1-p_0} (\sigma(p')) dp' \tag{19}$$

$$Q + 1 + \frac{\phi^2}{2} = F_1 \int_{p_2-p_0}^{p_1-p_0} (a' + a'')^4 dp' + F_2 \int_{p_2-p_0}^{p_1-p_0} (a' + a'')^3 dp' \tag{20}$$

Equation (20) can be solved if the form of the function $a''(p - p_0)$ is known. If the stress or tension $T(a'')$ in the tube wall is known as a function of a'' then $a''(p')$ can be found using the equilibrium condition (Rubinow and Keller [20])

$$\frac{T(a'')}{a''} = p - p_0 \tag{21}$$

IV Application to flow through an artery

Flow through an artery is determined by the static pressure-volume relation of a 4 cm long piece of the human external iliac artery, and converted into a tension versus length curve. From Rubinow and Keller [20] we have

$$T(a'') = t_1(a'' - 1) + t_2(a'' - 1)^5 \tag{22}$$

Where $t_1 = 13$ and $t_2 = 300$. By substituting (22) into (21), we get

$$dp' = \left[\frac{t_1}{a''^2} + t_2 \left(4a''^3 - 15a''^2 + 20a'' - 10 + \frac{1}{a''^2} \right) \right] da'' \tag{23}$$

Using equation (23), equation (20) can be written as

$$Q + 1 + \frac{\phi^2}{2} = F_1 \int_{p_2-p_0}^{p_1-p_0} (a' + a'')^4 \left[\frac{t_1}{a''^2} + t_2 \left(4a''^3 - 15a''^2 + 20a'' - 10 + \frac{1}{a''^2} \right) \right] da'' + F_2 \int_{p_2-p_0}^{p_1-p_0} (a' + a'')^3 \left[\frac{t_1}{a''^2} + t_2 \left(4a''^3 - 15a''^2 + 20a'' - 10 + \frac{1}{a''^2} \right) \right] da'' \tag{24}$$

$$Q = -1 - \frac{\phi^2}{2} + \{g(a_1'') - g(a_2'')\} \tag{25}$$

$$g(a'') = F_1 \left\{ \begin{aligned} & t_1 \left[-\frac{a'^4}{a''} + \frac{a''}{3} + 2a'a''^2 + 6a'^2a'' + 4a'^3 \log a'' \right] + \\ & a' \left(\frac{16}{7} a''^7 - 10a''^6 + 16a''^5 - 10a''^4 + 2a''^2 \right) \\ & a'^2 \left(4a''^6 - 18a''^5 + 30a''^4 - 20a''^3 + 6a'' \right) \\ & t_2 \left[a'^3 \left(\frac{16}{5} a''^5 - \frac{30}{2} a''^4 + \frac{80}{3} a''^3 - 20a''^2 + 4 \log a'' \right) \right. \\ & \left. a'^4 \left(a''^4 - 5a''^3 + 10a''^2 - 10a'' - \frac{1}{a''} \right) \right. \\ & \left. \frac{a''^8}{2} - \frac{15}{7} a''^7 + \frac{10}{3} a''^6 - 2a''^5 + \frac{a''^3}{3} \right] \end{aligned} \right\} + F_2 \left\{ \begin{aligned} & t_1 \left[-\frac{a'^4}{a''} + \frac{a''}{3} + 2a'a''^2 + 6a'^2a'' + 4a'^3 \log a'' \right] \\ & a' \left(2a''^6 - 9a''^5 + 15a''^4 - 10a''^3 + 3a'' \right) + \\ & a'^2 \left(\frac{12}{5} a''^5 - \frac{45}{4} a''^4 + 20a''^3 - 15a''^2 + 3 \log a'' \right) + \\ & + t_2 \left[a'^3 \left(a''^4 - 5a''^3 + 10a''^2 - 10a'' - \frac{1}{a''} \right) \right. \\ & \left. \frac{4a''^7}{7} - \frac{5}{2} a''^6 + 4a''^5 - \frac{5}{2} a''^4 + \frac{a''^2}{2} \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{26}$$

where $a'(z) = 1 + \phi \sin 2\pi(z - t)$, $a_1'' = a''(p_1 - p_0)$ and $a_2'' = a''(p_2 - p_0)$. We notice that equation (25) reduces to the corresponding results of Rubinow and Keller [20] for the flow of Newtonian fluid ($a' = 0, \tau = 0$) in an elastic tube. Also it is evident that the above equation reduces to the corresponding results of Sreenadh et al. for the peristaltic flow of viscous fluid ($\tau = 0, \beta = 0$) in an elastic tube.

V Results and discussion

In the present study, the peristaltic transport of a Bingham fluid flow through an elastic tube with permeable walls is investigated. The effects of various pertinent parameters like amplitude ratio ϕ , elastic parameters t_1 and t_2 , inlet

elastic radius α_1'' and outlet elastic radius α_2'' on flux Q are discussed graphically. The variation of flux for various values of elastic parameters t_1 and t_2 are shown in figures 2 and 3. The flux increases with higher values of both elastic parameters t_1 and t_2 respectively. Figure 4 illustrates the variation of flux for different values of yield stress parameter. It is observed that the flux decreases with increasing yield stress parameter. The variation of flux for different values of amplitude ratio ϕ is presented in Figure 5. It is noticed that the flux increases with higher values of amplitude ratio. From figure 6, it is noticed that the flux increases with greater values of slip parameter β . Figure 7 illustrates the flux variation as a function of inlet and external pressure difference. That is for higher values of outlet pressure $p_2 - p_0$ the flux increases. But the opposite behavior is noticed in the case of inlet pressure. The flux as a function of outlet pressure decreases as inlet pressure $p_1 - p_0$ increases which is presented in figure 8. Figures 9 to 14 Shows the variation of volumetric flow rate with respect to z . With increasing values of elastic parameters, flux increases which is evident from the Figures 9 and 10. From Figure 11, it is evident that the increasing of yield stress reduces the flux. Figure 12 shows the effect of ϕ on the flux. It is observed that flux increases with ϕ . The role of β on the flux is evident from the Figure 13 and shows that the flux increases with β . Variation of flux with respect to inlet and outlet pressures are represented in Figures 14 and 15. Flux decreases with increasing values of inlet pressure for a fixed outlet pressure. Opposite behavior is noticed in the case of increasing values of outlet pressure. This phenomenon exists due to the mechanism of peristaltic pumping. From Figure 16, it is evident that the results are good in agreement with the results of Sreenadh et al. (21) for $\tau = 0$, $\beta = 0$.

VI Conclusions

The present paper deals with the peristaltic transport of a Bingham fluid through a tube with elastic permeable wall, study the changes in the biofluid flow pattern in a biological duct with elastic wall. Biofluid is modeled as a Bingham fluid. We have the following observations:

1. The flux increases with the increasing of elastic parameters.
2. Flux decreases with an increase in the values of yield stress.
3. The flux increases with increasing values of amplitude ratio.
4. Inlet and outlet pressure shows opposite behavior on the flux.

Figure 2. Flux vs Radius for fixed values of $t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \tau = 0.5, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \phi = 0.6$.

Figure 3. Flux vs Radius for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, z = 0.1, \tau = 0.5, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \phi = 0.6$.

Figure 4. Flux vs Radius for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \phi = 0.6$.

Figure 5. Flux vs Radius for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5$.

Figure 6. Flux vs Radius for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5, \phi = 0.6$.

Figure 7. Flux vs inlet pressure for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5, \phi = 0.6$

Figure 8. Flux vs outlet pressure for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5, \phi = 0.6$.

Figure 9. Flux vs z for fixed values of $t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5, \phi = 0.4$.

Figure 1.10. Flux vs z for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, z = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5, \phi = 0.4$

Figure 11. Flux vs z for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \phi = 0.4$

Figure 12. Flux vs z for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5$

Figure 13. Flux vs z for fixed values of $t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \phi = 0.4, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5$

Figure 14. Flux vs z for fixed values of

$t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \phi = 0.4, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5, a_2^{II} = 1$

Figure 15. Flux vs z for fixed values of

$t_1 = 13, t_2 = 300, z = 0.1, \phi = 0.4, t = 0.01, \tau = 0.5, a_1^{II} = 0.5$

Figure 16. Flux vs z for fixed values of $t_1 = 13$, $t_2 = 300$

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